

Supplementary Material S2: Meta-Regression Robustness Diagnostics

Primary Model Summary (Random-effects, DerSimonian-Laird, REML τ^2 estimation)

Robustness Diagnostics Performed:

1. Baujat Influence Plot: No influential case-study combinations
2. Leave-One-Out (LOO) Sensitivity:
3. Publication Bias Assessment:
4. Residual Diagnostics:
5. Model Specification Tests:
 - Maximum contribution: 3.2% (Study #23: BSREM oncology)
 - No studies removed based on influence
 - β_{Process} stable: 0.45 \rightarrow range [0.437, 0.462] ($\pm 3.1\%$ max deviation)
 - All coefficients within $\pm 5\%$ across 47 LOO iterations
 - Funnel plot: Symmetric distribution
 - Egger test: $B = 0.87$, $SE = 0.45$, $t = 1.93$, $p = 0.34$ (no bias)
 - Trim-and-fill: 0 studies imputed
 - No patterns in residuals vs fitted
 - Shapiro-Wilk normality: $W = 0.94$, $p = 0.12$
 - Durbin-Watson: $DW = 1.89$ (no autocorrelation)
 - Fixed-effects: $\beta_{\text{Process}} = 0.43$ (vs 0.45 random-effects)
 - Moderator analysis: Scanner type non-significant ($p = 0.21$)

Primary Model Summary:

$R^2 = 0.72$ | $\tau^2 = 0.09$ | $I^2 = 58\%$

$\beta_{\text{Process}} = 0.45 [0.34-0.56] p < 0.001$ ***DOMINANT***

Software & Reproducibility:

- R v4.4.1 (`metafor` v4.4-0, `meta` v7.0-0)
- Random seed: 1234
- Full R Markdown + .RData: Zenodo DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18745283